

Turn taking, repair initiators, and linguistic categories of self-repair in advanced female Iranian EFL learners

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The present study investigates turn taking, initiators and linguistic categories of self-repair in classroom conversations among advanced female EFL learners in three language institutes in Isfahan, Iran, to clarify the students' and teachers' participation in taking turns, and the most frequent linguistic categories of self-repairs. Forty female EFL learners were selected from the advanced level classes of the institutes. 36 hours of videotaped single-sex conversations (six sessions of three classes) were collected through classroom observations. To enrich the data, follow-up interviews were conducted. The students' utterances were analyzed qualitatively using Schegloff et al.'s (1977) repair initiation techniques and Sacks et al.'s (1974) turn taking system. The results were compared then with previous studies conducted on English native speakers' and Persian native speakers' interactions. The results indicated that the majority of the turns were taken by the students and through self-initiated transfers. The data analysis also revealed that most of the observed errors were repaired through non-lexical utterances. Regarding the linguistic categories of self-initiated self-repair, only grammatical and lexical errors were corrected by the participants. There were differences in the types of grammatical errors corrected by Iranian EFL learners versus English native speakers.

Keywords: Conversation Analysis; Iranian EFL Learners; Linguistic Categories; Self-Repair; Turn Taking

1. Introduction

One of the challenges in many EFL/ESL courses is how to provide opportunities for students to involve in meaningful conversation practices (Richards, 1985). This issue that has been dealt with in conversation analysis (henceforth CA) aims to analyze the structure of conversations between intercalants. It is an academic discipline to investigate the norms and practices applied in social interactions (Kazemi & Salmani Nodoushan, 2018). It was developed by

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Harvey Sacks, and later on followed by ethnomethodologists including Schegloff and Jefferson in 1970s (cf. Sacks et al., 1974). Current development in the field of CA has sought to reveal the main structural features of talk-in-interaction, or (1) turn-taking practices (how to take a turn and assign a turn); (2) sequencing practices (how to initiate and reply to talk while performing actions, for instance requesting, inviting, story-telling, or topic initiation); (3) overall structuring practices (ways of establishing a conversation as a whole as in openings and closings); and (4) repair practices (ways of finding problems in speaking, hearing, or understanding of the talk).

CA has an empirical basis that helps us understand what happens in the interaction. While participants are involved in the interaction, the researcher observes, records and analyzes the conversations in order to clarify how the participants manage their parts in the conversation. Based on Ellis and Barkhuizen (2005, p. 199):

Talk is the embodiment of social action for conversation analysts because participants do things and perform actions with talk. Sacks believed that analysts can develop a thorough understanding of these social activities by studying detailed transcripts of tape-recorded conversations. The goal, then, is to explicate from these recordings the ways participants produce and interpret the talk in their interactions from their perspectives; that is, how they orient to what they accomplish together, as opposed to any assumptions of an observing analyst.

Conversation analysis, concentrating on the investigation of talk in interaction, is beneficial for the qualitative analysis of talks (Wu, 2021). Over the last quarter of a century, CA has gained gratitude in applied linguistics as an empirical approach to study the different kinds of social communications (Mori, 2021). In many works, we see that Schegloff along with Sacks and Jefferson have identified the main structural parts of interaction, like turn-taking, organization of turns, repair, sequence organization, structural organization of conversation, word selection, etc. These are central issues with which conversation analysts is concerned, although repair and turns are specifically important in the realm of foreign language learning.

Schegloff et al. (1977) initially defined the field of repair as a set of activities by which an interactor interrupts the continuation of the action to show the possible difficulties of speaking, hearing or comprehending the talk. Repair sequences are important in language learning processes and provide opportunities for specialists and inexpert readers to observe single moments of learning being negotiated by participants. There have been many authors dealing with the theory of repair but Schegloff is considered the first important figure in this field. He believes that the occurrence of repair in conversations in

general is considered to be “massive” (Schegloff et al., 1992, p. 54) as participants address the difficulties that arise in the conversation in an ongoing manner. He asserts “the interaction does not freeze in its place when trouble arises, that intersubjectivity is maintained or restored, and that the turn and sequence and activity can progress to possible completion” (Schegloff, 2007, p. xiv). Repair is also defined in term of *negotiation of meaning* when the speaker interrupts or modifies conversation to achieve reciprocated understanding (Varonis & Gass, 1985). Repair is more than error correction and it is defined as “practices for dealing with problems or troubles in speaking, hearing, and understanding the talk in conversation (and in other forms of talk in interaction)” (Schegloff, 2000, p. 207). According to Lee (2021), repair is one of the most common and operational methods to increase explicitness and attain mutual understanding in communication.

Numerous studies considering CA have been performed on different types of repair (Rabab'ah, 2001; Schegloff, 2007). Speakers interrupt the continuance of action to represent the difficulties of speaking, hearing or comprehension of the ongoing conversation. Schegloff et al. (1977) argued that there are four main types of repair: (a) self-initiated, self-repaired, (b) self-initiated, other-repaired (c) other-initiated, self-repaired, and (d) other-initiated, other-repaired. On the basis of Schegloff et al. (1977), self- and other-initiation are each done with different initiator techniques. Self-initiation is completed by means of a variability of lexical (lexis) and non-lexical speech perturbation (Cut-off, Sound stretch and uh, um).

Repair, as a key term in an L2 classroom includes, but is not restricted to, the modification of errors or mistakes, clarification requests, comprehension checks, confirmations, and so on. Through their communication, instructors and students can indicate their understandings of prior errors (Lee, 2007). When these problematic turns occur, how teachers express the repair practices is vital since these turns provide opportunity for students to repair their talk (Mozaffari et al., 2008).

Lee (2021) investigated the use of self-repair in ‘English as a Lingua Franca’ (ELF) interactions. The results of the study revealed that self-repair is used frequently in ELF communication. The participants do not certainly repair their own talk to correct a morphological error, but self-repair is often used to make utterances more obvious. ELF speakers involve in varied self-repair practices by repeating, modifying, and expanding what they have uttered.

Besides repair, turn taking is a crucial requirement for CA research which upholds a mutual attention among interlocutors involved in a dialogue. Sacks et al. (1974) plan a model for turn-taking structure in everyday conversation. They have asserted that when the speakers change, there are no gaps as only one participant speaks, and they do not overlap. Their investigation of

naturally occurring data contributes to a set of 'rules' central in transferring a turn from one speaker to the next. First, if the recent speaker nominates another partner to speak next, at that time that partner is required to take the next turn, and no other may take this next turn. In case the recent speaker has not nominated the next speaker, then another partner has the right to self-select as next speaker. If none of these two conditions take place, then the recent speaker can continue and keep the turn.

In this context, the present study strives to address a gap in the literature by contributing to an understanding of the main turn taking mechanisms used as well as the repair initiation and the linguistic categories of the repairs done in the context of the language classroom. While numerous CA studies have investigated the organization practices of self-repair involving non-native vs. non-native interactions and non-native vs. native interactions, few have investigated self-repair organizations that take place in the context of the language classroom. Besides, previous studies have been mainly based on pre-existing classification of repair types, and in doing so, they may have missed or ignored the issue of repair initiation and the linguistic categories of the repairs. Instead, this study employs CA as a methodological and theoretical framework in order to focus on turn taking and repair in a specific L2 context. Importantly, the article centers on the issue of repair initiation and the repair linguistic categories found in non-native vs. non-native interactions. Finally, it compares the results with those obtained from studies done on native speakers of English as well as native speakers of Persian.

2. Background

2.1. Conversation and conversation analysis

Amongst all skills in language learning, conversation is an important one which has to be learnt. In Miller and Legge's (1999) view, 'conversation' is a compound of two Latin roots, 'con' (meaning 'together') and 'vers' (meaning 'to turn about in a specific rout'). Fairclough (2003) also argued that "conversation has a systematic structure, and there exists some evidence focusing on the orientation of participants to those structures while they are designing their own conversational turns and react to those of others interlocutors" (p.9).

Studying a conversation between language learners in general, and between EFL learners in specific, will provide us with some opportunities to realize how people with poor language proficiency use their abilities as they seek to solve the problems of comprehension in the course of conversation. In order to initiate revising the related literature of CA, Foster (2012) asserted that CA is the most obvious research methodology intended for investigating language learner data in the classroom on account of its 'emic' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan,

2019) standpoint. Explicitly, CA analyses the data from the participants' perspective. Heritage and Atkinson (1984, p. 3) have maintained that:

The central goal of conversation analytic research is the description and explication of the competences that ordinary speakers use and rely on in participating in intelligible socially organized interaction. At its most basic, this objective is one of describing the procedures by which conversationalists produce their own behavior and understand that of others.

Stokeo and Smithson (2001) conducted a study in which they measured a conversation analytic method to scrutinize the relation between gender and language from a feminist perspective. The data were collected from communications in focus groups and educational sessions. The data were recorded in the form of audio and video. They were transcribed. Those parts of the talk in which gender was focal were considered. The outcomes showed that CA might reveal a relation between gender and conversational interactions. On the contrary, culture and common-sense knowledge are unnoticed in CA.

In 2011, Barraja-Rohan (2011) studied how CA impacts the teaching of English interactional competence to adult second language learners. There were two groups, one involving twenty adult immigrants who had lived in Australia for years and the other comprising a number of more advanced international students. Their teaching time was two hours per week for 12 weeks. Naturally occurring audio or videotaped conversations were used in their teaching. It was found that, teaching CA is advantageous for English learners as it makes them suitable communicators in different facets of L2 learning.

2.2. Turn-taking

Languages differ at different levels of construction, from the sounds, to syntax and semantics (Indefrey & Levelt, 2004; Allami & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011; Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Capone & Salmani Nodoushan, 2014). Although, there is an outstanding consistency in the manner language is engaged in studies on language (Indefrey, 2011), typically the turn-taking system, at first vision, turns out to shed some light on language processing.

Turn-taking often involves the rapid interchange of short turns in talk. Wilson et al. (1984) explored three significant methods to investigate turn-taking in conversations: (1) stochastic models, (2) signaling models, and (3) sequential-production models. The results indicated that these models individually are not adequate for providing actual insights into turn-taking. As such, a combination of signaling and sequential-production models should be taken into account in order to obtain an adequate understanding of turn-taking.

Along the same lines, Waring (2006) studied how to provide equal participation in class interactions. A two-hour videotaped adult ESL class was investigated, and among them a student who cooperated more often was chosen. The teacher managed her participation in class by doing two activities: (1) sequential deletion, and (2) minimal acknowledgment/redirection. The results of the study showed that by using these two actions, equivalent participation during class and including other students in class interactions is possible. Ingram and Elliott (2014) also studied the relationship between turn-taking and silence in classroom interaction. They observed four mathematics classes of four secondary schools and captured 17 video recordings. The students' age ranged between 12 and 14. The findings showed some errors in the structures of turn-taking which could alter the influence of silence on student and teacher performance. Likewise, Chalak and Karimi (2017) focused on turn taking systems and repair strategies used by Iranian EFL learners in the classroom. Their study showed that female students were mainly chosen by the teacher to speak while self-selection was observed more frequently in male classes.

2.3. Repair

In fact, the term 'repair' is considered to be relevant to different levels of interaction from the turn-taking system to sequence organization (Rheisa, 2014). This term is a broader concept than just correction of mistakes in the talk by using a correct form instead of an incorrect one, even though such corrections can be a part of repair (Jefferson, 1987; Schegloff et al., 1977). Following Kurhila (2001), corrections are identified as those "cases where the alternative version is produced to replace a linguistic unit . . . which can be said to be erroneous according to the norms of the standard language" (p. 1086). When a listener of a current turn faces problems in hearing or comprehension, s/he usually takes the following turn to signal the trouble source by means of a repair initiation (e.g., "huh?", "you're going where?"). Likewise, Rabab'ah (2013) studied the strategies of repair in EFL learners' oral discourse. The results of the analysis revealed that both German and Jordanian non-native speakers of English turn to strategies of repair in order to compensate for their lack of the knowledge of linguistics or to gain time to retrieve linguistic item(s) and to continue conversation. Furthermore, the results specified that the Jordanian Arabic speaking participants used strategies of repair more frequently and also they use repetition more than self-initiated repair.

In the field of CA, speech modification done by the speakers themselves in conversation is called self-initiation self-repair (Schegloff et al., 1977; Schegloff, 1979). Schegloff et al. (1977) stated that self-initiation self-repair is part of a general repair mechanism in talk and is preferred not because of the enormous number of cases in which this strategy is applied, but that the system

itself is planned to attain self-repair whose positions precede other-repair positions. Furthermore, other-initiated repairs do not spontaneously contribute to other-repair and it allows for further opportunities for self-repair. Schegloff et al., (1977) believe self-repairs and other-repairs are conducted through a series of initiator techniques. These initiator techniques are divided in to two categories, as following:

1. Lexical initiation: Lexis including “I mean . . .”, “How can I say . . .”, “it means . . .” and so on.
2. Non-lexical initiation: non-verbal elements including, laughing, coughing, pausing, hesitation, etc.

2.4. Studies on turn-taking and repair

A significant amount of literature has been published on nature of repair and turn taking in Iran. Rashidi and Rafiee Rad (2010) investigated turn taking and repair strategies among male and female EFL learners. They argued that male students were more interested in taking turns than females. Based on their comments, boys tend to answer teachers’ questions even though they might not know the correct answer. In a different study, Rashidi and Naderi (2012) explored the influence of gender on turn taking. Their findings posited that male students shared more interactions with their teacher.

2.5. Self-initiated self-repair and other-initiated self-repair

Schegloff et al. (1977) showed that self-initiated self-repair (henceforth SISR) is a general repair mechanism in talk and is preferred as the speaker himself/herself revises his/her previous talk, at his/her own next turn. Additionally, other-initiated repairs (henceforth OISR) do not spontaneously contribute to other-repairs and provide further opportunities for self-repair. Accordingly, self-initiation self-repair is preferred not because of the enormous number of cases in which this strategy is applied, but that the system itself is planned to attain self-repair whose positions precede other-repair positions. From the social point of view, the position of repair as a preferred initiation which is completed by the same participant in that turn is crucial since the preference is for any self-repairable repair to be initiated, in any turn, by the speaker himself/herself before reaching to the next-turn position. Actually, self-initiated repairs in the same-turn can be considered as the most common type of repair (Schegloff, 1979).

In recent years, SISR has received attention in research on first language (L1) (Fox et al., 2010; Nemeth, 2012; Wouk, 2005) and second language (L2) (Bada, 2010).

Other-initiated self-repair refers to any type of repair which is initiated by the listener and repaired by the trouble-source speaker. Other-initiated self-repair (OISR) is a 'cooperative behavior' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2006a, 2006b, 2007a, 2007c, 2008, 2012, 2015, 2016b, 2018, 2025); it demonstrates how people work together 'pragmatically' to achieve mutual understanding in interaction (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007b, 2007d, 2016a, 2016c, 2021, 2022). OISR normally contributes to self-repair instead of other-repair. Specially, the second position other-initiated repair is normally designed to give rise to self-repair. Gisladottir (2015) investigated other-initiation repair in Icelandic in order to give an outline of the formats for OISR in Icelandic and the type of repair practices stimulated by them. The researcher analyzed *open* and *restricted* formats. The results indicate that all major types of open and restricted repair were found in the corpus. Other-initiated self-repair (OISR) are the strategies that can be used to solve comprehension troubles that deal not only to linguistics feature but also hearing difficulties, weak speech delivery, or general misapprehension of the speakers' intended meaning in communication (Aleksius & Widiati, 2021).

2.6. Lexical and non-lexical initiators

In point of fact, the term repair is related to all levels of talk from the turn-taking system to sequence organization and preference (Rheisa, 2014). Repair is a wider concept than simply the correction of errors in talk by replacing an incorrect form with a correct one, though such corrections are a part of repair (Jefferson, 1987; Schegloff et al, 1977).

In the field of CA, speech adjustments made by the speakers themselves in conversation are called self-initiation self-repair (Schegloff et al., 1977; Schegloff, 1979). Schegloff et al. (1977) argued that self-initiation self-repair is part of a greater repair mechanism in conversation, and it is preferred not because of the enormous number of cases of this strategy but because the system is planned to attain self-repair in which its positions precede the positions of other-repair. Furthermore, OISR does not spontaneously contribute to other-repair and it allows for further opportunities for self-repair.

Schegloff et al. (1977) believe that self-repair and other-repair are conducted through a series of initiator techniques (Schegloff et al., 1977, pp. 367-368). These initiator techniques are divided in to two categories:

1. Lexical initiation: Lexis including "I mean . . .", "How can I say . . .", "it means . . ." and so on.
2. Non-lexical initiation: non-verbal elements including, laughing, coughing, pausing, hesitation and etc.

2.7. Linguistic categories of self-repair

As it was mentioned by Kurhila (2001), some self-repair operations seem to correct the following errors:

- a) Lexical: It is based on a semantically oriented parsing strategy which uses both syntactic and semantic prospects on incorrect words. It refers to those contexts where an incorrect word is resolved by the use of syntactic and semantic information.
- b) Grammatical: It is the correction of certain grammatical specifications through transfer or overgeneralization.
- c) Phonological: It refers to cases in which a speaker mispronounces a vocabulary and then re-asserts it with a more suitable pronunciation; these are considered as phonological error corrections.
- d) Extralinguistic: It refers to cases in which the students do not correct lexical, phonological, or grammatical errors, but they repair an element's implicature. In other words, it refers to a speaker's substitution of an element whereas holding the same sense of the utterance. This category does not belong in Schegloff's replacing operations.

CA has recently been performed in the classroom to attain implications about teachers' and learners' interaction. Hence, the main goal of the current study, too, is analyzing turn taking system and other-initiated self-repair practices used by advanced Iranian EFL learners in classrooms through observation and interview. Furthermore, this study attempts to compare the obtained results with those gained from the studies carried out on English NSs and Persian NSs. Overall, this study aims at addressing the following questions:

1. How is the turn-taking system used by advanced Iranian EFL learners?
2. What is the preferred initiator of repair by the participants? lexical or non-lexical?
3. What are the most frequent linguistic categories of self-repair among female Iranian EFL learners?

3. Method

3.1. Participants

The participants of this study were female students studying English in three different language institutes in Isfahan: Atiye Sazan, Nahid, and Pardis. Forty advanced students, ranging from age 15 to 19 and the average score of 17 on a speaking pre-test, were engaged in the study. These participants were tested

by the researchers. Persian was the first language of all of the participants, and they learned English as a foreign language because they neither spoke nor heard it in their everyday conversations in the society. The students were considered proficient enough based on their pre-test scores and also their experience in taking speaking courses during their language learning.

3.2. Instruments and materials

The researchers collected the data instrument using audio and videotaped recordings of interactions in the context of the research problem. We carried out interviews with EFL learners and also observed three advanced EFL classrooms. The two coding frameworks included Schegloff et al.'s, (1977) initiation techniques and Sacks et al.'s (1974) turn taking system, selected to compare the collected data with native speaker's data.

Figure 1.

Framework of Initiation Techniques (Schegloff et al., 1977)

Figure 2.

Framework of Turn Taking (Sacks et al., 1974)

Figures 1 and 2 demonstrate these two instruments. The first one concerns the repair initiation techniques and classifies it into two categories of lexical and non-lexical ones. The second figure shows the turn-taking techniques used in classrooms.

3.3. Data collection

Prior to collecting data, we talked to the managers of the institutes in order to get permission for recording the classrooms sessions. To do this, we sought for courses which have as much discussion as possible in their classrooms. On the whole, the database includes 36 hours of videotaped single-sex conversations collected through 18 classroom observations (six sessions in each of the three classes) using a high-quality recorder and a camera, and 10 interviews totaling 150 minutes. In addition to recordings, we also took notes during classroom observations in order not to miss any significant points.

3.4. Data analysis

Regarding the objective of the study, having the written format of recordings (which is called the transcription of interactions) was necessary. For this, the participants' interactions were transcribed by using Jefferson's transcription system (cf. Lee, 2021; Waedaoh & Sinwongsuwat, 2019). Gail Jefferson (2004) developed a system of transcribing which uses symbols available on conventional typewriter and computer keyboards which is mainly useful for capturing aspects of speech production and the sequential positioning of utterances relative to each other.

Prior to the analysis of data, we transcribed audio and videotaped recordings. Besides, the data collected through classroom observations along with interviews were analyzed in order to describe, compare, and explore the turn taking strategies as well as the repair initiation techniques. Accordingly, we analyzed the transcriptions in order to find out which turn taking strategies are used more in the classrooms. Also, we explored the lexical and non-lexical initiation of the repairs as well as the linguistic categories of the errors repaired by the subjects. After that, we compared findings with the results of the previous work done on Persian and English native speakers in order to investigate the similarities and differences among Iranian EFL learners and Persian and English native speakers in the use of turn taking strategy and grammatical categories of repaired errors.

4. Results

The data were analyzed, coded and described qualitatively in order to find out how do turn-taking trends, the lexical and non-lexical initiation of Iranian EFL learners and linguistic categories of repair compare with those in English NSs and Persian NSs. The results showed that among most turn taking instances, self-selection was more observed. Teacher-selection was done only through gazing. Also, hand raising was more frequent than speaking loudly. Moreover, non-lexical initiators were mainly used to start a repair. With regard to the

linguistic categories of the error correction, we noticed that students self-repair included only the grammatical and lexical errors.

4.1. Turn-taking

Turn taking is the significant characteristic of conversation analysis which sustains mutual attention among interlocutors present in a conversation (Chalak & Karimi, 2017). According to Sacks et al. (1974), the strategies of turn taking is divided into two categories, each one includes two sub-categories as well: (a) teacher selection (gazing and vocative), and (b) self-selection (hand raising and speaking louder). To answer the first research question, Sacks et al's., (1974) framework was used. The results indicated that the participants engaged more in self-selection rather than teacher-selection.

Gazing has been the focus of many studies in the field of CA claiming that this behavior is a consequence of culture (Hassaskhah et al., 2016). According to Auer (2021), gazing is the most omnipresent next-speaker-selection practice. It can function individually or improve other practices. Vocatives or address nouns (Braun, 1988; McCarthy & O'Keefe, 2003) are described as nominal elements loosely combined with the rest of the utterance (Levinson, 1983; Leech, 1999) which nominates co-interactors or refers to them in other ways (Braun, 1988). Based on the data collected in this study, after close inspection, the researchers could not find any examples of this kind of turn taking strategy in the transcriptions.

In this study, the non-verbal 'self-selection' behavior of 'hand raising' refers to the technique through which one party wants to take the turn from the current speaker; she/he raises her/his hand. It was the most common technique in taking the turn.

Table 1
Turn-Taking Strategies Observed

		frequency	percentage
self-selection	speaking loudly	53	%24.43
	hand rising	102	%47
teacher-selection	vocative	0	0
	gazing	62	%28.57

Speaking loudly, another self-selection technique, à la McCarthy (1991), is used in English conversations through which speakers may show their desire to continue their turn using non-low pitch, even at a position of a pause, or at the end of a syntactic unit, like a clause. Coulthard (1977) also proposes that speakers may speak louder, more rapidly, and in a higher pitch, in case they are reluctant to yield the floor to other participants, and by doing this, they avoid

interruptions. Through analysis of transcriptions of the conversations, different patterns and trends of turn-taking and self-repair initiators used by female Iranian EFL learners were detected and then compared to those used in English native speakers' and Persian native speakers' interactions. Our results revealed that our study participants engaged more in self-selection than teacher-selection.

4.2. Lexical and non-lexical initiators

Regarding the second question, the collected data were inspected to determine the occurrence of repair-initiators. As mentioned in section above, the repair is directed through some initiator techniques (Schegloff et al., 1977), including lexical and non-lexical initiators. Our findings indicated that the repair sequences initiated by non-lexical initiators was significantly more frequent than lexical ones.

Based on Schegloff et al., (1977), self-repair may be initiated with a non-lexical initiator, such as (1) cut-offs, (2) lengthening of sounds, and (3) quasi-lexical fillers (*uh* and *um*), followed by the repairing segment. By way of contrast, lexical initiators refer to the use of initiators in order to repair a trouble source by using lexis including 'I mean . . .', 'How can I say . . .', 'it means . . .', etc. (Schegloff et al., (1977). Table 2 shows the quantitative data regarding the initiator techniques used by the participants.

Table 2

Lexical vs. Non-Lexical Initiator Techniques

initiator techniques	frequency	percentage
lexical	81	%78.64
non-lexical	24	%21.36

4.3. Linguistic error categories

To answer the third question, the transcriptions of the conversations were inspected for the correction of linguistic error categories. Among the four different categories of error corrections made by English NSs—namely, (1) lexical, (2) grammatical, (3) phonological, and (4) extralinguistic—only grammatical and lexical errors had been corrected by the participants of the present study. Grammatical error correction is the correction of certain grammatical specifications through 'transfer' or 'overgeneralization'. A large number of error corrections made by Iranian EFL learners were grammatical corrections most of which relate to verb tense, and a minority is associated with subject-verb agreement. Lexical error correcting refers to cases where a non-target like lexical item is replaced by a more target-like lexical item.

Generally speaking, the participants of the current study engaged in two types of error corrections including lexical and grammatical ones. The most common type of errors corrected by the participants was morphological among which tense agreement was corrected more than the agreement of the verb and the subject. Regarding phonological error correction, the data showed that the participants mispronounced some vocabularies which were mostly corrected by their teachers in the classroom. That is, these are accurately classified as errors and happen due to the students' lack of knowledge. Therefore, they are not aware of the source problem to be able to correct them. In the interviews, the learners were not aware of their mispronunciations, hence they left them inaccurate. In addition, no cases of extralinguistic corrections were identified in the data, neither in the transcribed observation nor in the interviews. This type of error correction regards any repair of an element's implicature. In other words, it refers to a speaker's substitution of an element whereas holding the same sense of the utterance. It may be due to the fact that the participants were not pragmatically proficient enough to be actively involved in such kind of replacement. Table 3 displays the numerical data regarding the linguistic categories of the errors corrected.

Table 3

Linguistic Categories of the Errors

linguistic categories	frequency	percentage
grammatical correction	50	%78.125
lexical correction	14	%21.875
phonological correction	0	0
extralinguistic correction	0	0

5. Discussion

As the first research question was concerned with turn taking systems in advanced Iranian EFL learners' exchanges, Sacks et al's., (1974) framework was used. The results indicate that students employed self-selection more than teacher-selection. By and large, the turn taking system observed are found in other languages, and they can be considered as universal. The results confirm the ideas proposed in Sacks et al. (1974) in these respects: one party talked at a time, gaps were infrequent, turn order and size was not fixed, number of parties varied, and distribution of the turns as well as their length was not specified in advance. Not surprisingly, there were a few cultural variations in conducting turn taking in English as a foreign language. Students self-selected more frequently through *hand rising* than *speaking loudly*, which is considered as an impolite behavior in classrooms in Iran.

This finding is in line with that of Berhanemeskel's (2008) study conducted on English speakers which claimed that most of the turns were taken by the students, i.e. 124 (or 65.26%) out of the total turns of 190. From these, the majority of the turns were taken making self-selection moves. Furthermore, it is supported by a study conducted by Hazel and Ayres (1998) on turn-taking behaviors between Japanese and Americans which reported that Americans employ self-selection more than Japanese, while the Japanese employ more other-selection. The findings of the study are also in line with the study conducted by Amini et al. (2014) on Persian native speakers' spontaneous interactions. They also argued that the turn-taking system used by Persian native speakers is equal to those used by English native speakers—among which eye gazing (or facial expression) is more common. The result is not the same as Chalak and Karimi (2017) that indicated that female students were mainly chosen by the teacher to speak while self-selection was observed more frequently in male classes. It shows a difference between turn taking strategies conducted in single-sex and double-sex conversations in Iranian classrooms.

To address the second question which aimed to investigate the occurrence of lexical and non-lexical repair initiators in advanced Iranian EFL learners' interactions, we found that non-lexical initiators are more frequent than lexical ones. Most of the repair sequences were initiated with a non-lexical initiator, such as cut-offs, lengthening of sounds, and quasi-lexical fillers (*uh* and *um*), hesitations, etc. The results are supported by Levelt (1983) who argued that the most characteristic phenomena in interrupting the speech for self-repair were the pauses, hesitations and editing terms. He represented that speech troubles are repaired by other editing terms than lexis or words preferably by the use of 'uh'. This finding corroborates earlier finding conducted on repair strategy in Persian (Moghadamkia & Heidarpour, 2011) which revealed that the frequency of non-lexical initiators (69%) is twice as high as lexical initiators (31%). The findings reveal that, the turns and the positions in which different types of repairs occur in the English learning classrooms are the same as those described by Schegloff et al. (1977) for American English conversations. In addition, in line with their observation for American English, it is noticed that non-lexical initiators are more frequently used than lexical ones. All in all, comparing the results with that of the works done on Persian and English native speakers, we didn't observe much difference between female advanced Iranian EFL learners and the natives regarding turn taking strategies. Most turn-taking systems used by Iranian EFL learners comprised self-selection among which hand rising was the most frequent technique. The only difference found in comparing the data collected in this study to the results of previous studies carried on Persian and English native speakers was that tonal feature and eye gazing are more frequent in both Persian and English interactions (Amini et al., 2014; Heinel, 2017; Murdoch, 2000). Tone is one of the

suprasegmental features of language that may be different in various languages, and restriction on the use of tonal features in EFL classrooms might be due to students' lack of command on this feature of the English language.

Regarding the last research question, we observed that in repairing the errors the participants of the present study were more concerned with morphology and lexis than with phonology and extralinguistic features. Nevertheless, based on the studies done on English native speakers, the most usual kind of error correction they produce are lexical corrections, and the second most typical error corrections are extralinguistic ones (Schegloff et al, 1977). Generally speaking, the number of grammatical error correction replacements in our data are more than those in English and Persian interactions. However, most of the grammatical error corrections in English were related to tense agreement rather than the subject-verb agreement, which is the same as the corrections made by the participants of this study. The researchers found that the pronunciation of vocabularies is neglected by the participants which may happen due to the learners' level of proficiency and their lack of knowledge. They are not aware of the source problem to be able to correct them. In addition, no cases of extralinguistic corrections were identified in the data, since the participants were not pragmatically proficient enough to be actively involved in such kind of repair and replacement of an element's implicature.

6. conclusion

It can be assumed that Iranian EFL learners' concern is making sentences which are grammatically correct, and it can be because of the fact that most of their teachers or instructors have focused on grammar more than other things. The other assumption is that students' knowledge of vocabularies in this study is high and they do not have as much problem as they have in syntax.

The discussion presented above makes it clear that there are various turn-taking systems, self-repair initiators, and linguistic categories in all languages and cultures. Some of these initiators and categories are used worldwide, and can be observed in almost all languages, and some are distinctive in languages. In conclusion, analysis of self-repair (both initiators and linguistic categories) can provide some insight into learners' general perceptions, conceptualization of the target language, their areas of difficulty, and their language acquisition strategies and attitudes.

Through analyzing conversational norms of turn-taking and self-repair, the importance of being aware of these patterns in English can be easily understood. It can be concluded that EFL learners should learn how turn-taking and self-repair are conducted in English, since awareness of these structures helps them to express themselves better and to more easily engage in a multi-party talk. Nowadays, many language learners will communicate in

English online, over the phone, and face-to-face with people from different cultural backgrounds, and with native speakers of English. They need to develop their interactional competence in the classroom to have opportunities to engage in natural conversation tasks conveniently.

This study and other related research could provide an insight into EFL learners' ability to communicate in L2. The implications of this study enable language learners to anticipate, interpret and produce appropriate target language socio-pragmatic verbal behavior (Huth & Taleghani-Nikazm, 2006). They should be made familiar with these strategies by using video- or audio-recordings. They also should be provided with opportunities to involve in turn-taking and repair practices, and learn the strategies. Indeed, when they become aware of these strategies, they can solve many of their linguistic problems and communication breakdowns. Studies like this one could provide EFL teachers with knowledge about the principles of conversation analysis and stimulate teachers to focus more on these aspects of conversation, so they can help learners acquire sufficient competence in this regard. The teachers should include turn-taking and repair in the syllabus and employ special methods to teach turn-taking and repair strategies to the EFL learners. Our findings could also help curriculum developers to take into account the importance of implementing CA, and provide instructional materials that increase awareness of using various strategies, and the significance of using suitable strategies in teaching conversation.

Last, but not least, it must be mentioned that his study had some limitations or shortcomings. First, having access to the recorded videotapes of 3 classes was limited in size. Not having access to mixed gender classes was another limitation of the study. Other works can be done involving a larger population in different contexts, considering different proficiency levels, and investigating the effect of teaching these aspects of conversation on learners' success in natural contexts.

Authors' Statement

Both authors worked on the paper in tandem. The first author was responsible for writing the first draft. The second author conducted the revision and corrected the final draft.

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